

UPCOMING TRENDS IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY SPECIAL REFERENCE TO GENERIC MEDICINE IN INDIA

DR. Shaikh Abid Dilawar

*Assistant Professor NKSP's
Institute of Management Badnapur.
Dist.Jalna*

INTRODUCTION

A generic medicine is a copy of the original branded product. Once the patent for the original product has run out, the pharmaceutical company who developed the medicine no longer has the exclusive right to produce and distribute the medicine. Other pharmaceutical companies are able to create their own version of the medicine. The type and quantity of the active ingredient in the generic product is the same as the branded version, but the inactive ingredients are slightly different. The generic medicine is sold under a different brand name and it may look different (e.g. in colour or shape) to the original.

A generic medicine is a copy of the original branded product. Once the patent for the original product has run out, the pharmaceutical company who developed the medicine no longer has the exclusive right to produce and distribute the medicine. Other pharmaceutical companies are able to create their own version of the medicine. The type and quantity of the active ingredient in the generic product is the same as the branded version, but the inactive ingredients are slightly different. The generic medicine is sold under a different brand name and it may look different (e.g. in colour or shape) to the original.

PSEUDO-GENERIC MEDICINES

A pseudo-generic product is not a remake of the original; it is an exact replica of the original. It is made by the same company with exactly the same ingredients in the same way. The only difference is the name and packaging.

These medicines are usually marketed by the same manufacturer at the same price as the original. Pharmaceutical companies make pseudo-generic products to combat true generics and to discourage competitor pharmaceutical companies from entering the market for that particular medicine.

PRIME MINISTER NARENDRA MODI ON GENERIC MEDICINE

Monday said that the government would put in place a legal framework to ensure doctors prescribe low cost generic

medicines to patients. "Doctors write prescriptions in such a way that poor people do not understand the handwriting and he has to buy that medicine from private stores at high prices," Modi said while inaugurating a multi-speciality hospital in Surat. "We will bring in a legal framework by which if a doctor writes a prescription, he has to write in it that it will be enough for patients to buy generic medicines and he need not buy any other medicines". Experts say more than 70% of the over Rs 1 lakh crore domestic pharmaceutical market is dominated by branded generics, whereas patented drugs make up 9%. As with demonetization, the PM sought to underline that he was ready to take on influential interests to push for "pro-poor" causes. "We have done this work, and you can imagine how angry the manufacturers of medicines will be. Despite the wrath of a very powerful lobby, the government is taking one step after another so that poor people and middle class get quality health services," Modi said.

The PM outlined a series of measures planned by the health ministry in line to regulate cost of medical care in the country with recent price control or caps on medical devices being one such initiative. The health ministry has recently issued a draft gazette notification making it mandatory for pharma companies to carry generic name of drugs on packs that is at least two fonts larger than the brand name. "This clause will be a legal provision as a rule under the existing Drugs and Cosmetics Act and any violation will be punishable under the provisions of the law," a senior health ministry official told TOI. The ministry has sought public comments on the draft within 45 days, after which it is likely to become part of the drug law. Besides, the ministry has also issued orders to the Medical Council of India (MCI), state governments and all central government hospitals asking them to ensure that doctors write prescriptions with generic names of medicines in legible hand writing. The move assumes significance as medicines account for 70-75% of a household's out of pocket expenditure on health. While generic medicines are good quality low cost drugs with equal efficacy as branded drugs, doctors and chemists often push the more expensive alternatives. Despite stringent price control, big pharmaceutical companies manage to spend exorbitantly on marketing and branding of their drugs. Since advertisement of

prescription medicines are not allowed in India, companies or medical representatives push their products through doctors, chemists and distributors in lieu of freebies, junkets and incentives. Modi said his government brought in a health policy after 15 years and capped the prices of medicines and stents, which has not gone down well with some pharmaceutical companies.

PROS AND CONS:

Generic drugs seem to be getting more and more popular when it comes to major brand name drugs, including many medications related to heart health like statins and blood pressure medication. But exactly how safe are generic drugs when it comes to staying heart healthy? Let's look at some of the pros and cons of generic medication below.

PROS:

- Cheaper prices. The main reason so many people buy generic drugs is because they are so much cheaper than brand name drugs. Brand name drugs require research and testing that take a lot of time and money, but generic drugs only need to copy what already exists, saving them the cost and allowing the price to stay low.
- Bioequivalent. Biologically speaking, generic drugs must meet strict guidelines so that the same amount of active ingredient is delivered to the body at the same time, and used by the body, in the same way as the brand name product.
- FDA approved. The FDA sets stringent guidelines and performs research on generic drugs to make sure that they are bioequivalent to the brand name.
- Heart Healthy. According to a recent study, generic heart medications show the same medical results as brand name medications.

CONS:

- Contamination. Generic drugs are often produced in factories in countries like India, China, or other areas with cheap labor and overhead. The conditions at these factories have sometimes contaminated drugs, leading to recalls in the United States. To be fair however, there have been a handful of cases where even US based brand name medications had similar issues although probably not nearly as often.
- Oversight. According to a report by the Government Accountability Office, these foreign factories sometimes escape rigorous FDA inspections, dodge documentation of their practices, and don't receive follow-up monitoring even when serious manufacturing or drug-handling problems have

been identified. Usually only one manufacturer produces a brand name drug whereas several manufacturers can produce a generic drug. While the FDA insists on bioequivalence of the active drug, there sometimes can be subtle differences in the delivery system of the drug or non-active "fillers" for the drug. These differences rarely result in any clinically meaningful problem for the patient although in rare instances a patient might have a sensitivity or intolerance to a different filler or delivery system.

- Mixing up the pills. As brand medications typically have a consistent "branded" look to them that patients can get familiar and comfortable with, generics often do not look as familiar or it is not as obvious what each pill is. Furthermore, when a prescription is refilled, if the medication is made by a different generic manufacturer and has a different appearance, this can lead to medication confusion and errors or even patients not taking the pills they are prescribed. Click here for more on this.

- Doctors remain divided. Many medical professionals (albeit a relative minority) are still divided on the use of generic drugs for heart disease, leaving some lingering doubt in this area. Some specific medications including thyroid supplements and blood thinners have had evidence of true clinically meaningful problems when switching between brand and generic or between different generics.

More and more frequently patients find their brand name prescription medication will not be covered by their insurance plan or their co-pay is higher. Often, the insurer will offer a generic version at a co-pay that is less. Fortunately, at this point, the vast majority of cardiac medications are available in generic form with generally no obvious problem for the vast majority of patients.

When our patients start on a new medication that is available from a generic manufacturer, we usually recommend starting with the generic form if there is no scientific consensus that the brand name version is any better. While usually the patient will also save money directly, we all benefit from the aggregate reduction in health care costs. If a patient has been on a brand medication and can save money by switching to the generic formulation or even a less expensive brand of the same drug class, it usually can be done without any ill effects but we believe it ultimately should be the patient's decision after conferring with their physicians. Some patients prefer not to "rock the boat" and not make the switch. While that is not unreasonable, one has to weight whether it is worth the extra cost.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Keegan J. Warren (2008):

The author in this has give n product development assets which he pinpointed as, the pressure for globalization is intense when new products require major investments and long periods of development time. The pharmaceuticals industry provisions of sticking illusion of dewing force. According to pharmaceutical manufacturers association (PMA), the cost of developing a new drug in 1976 was \$54 million; by 1982, the cost had increased to 87\$ million. By 1993, the cost of developing a new drug had reached \$35 million.

Such costs must be recovered in the global marketplace, as do single national market is likely enough to support investments of this size. As noted earlier, global marketing doesn't necessary mean operating everywhere; in the \$200 billion pharmaceutical industry, for example seven countries accounts for 75 percent of sales.

Keegan J. Warren (2008) Global Marketing Management., Prentice Hall, inc. ISBN-97-8-81-203-2066-6

Nargundkhar Rajendra (2008):

In his study, the author has given in the fifth chapter about the world class brands/marketers in Indian, which he has been highlighten on the Paras Pharma deserves to be recognized for its clever marketing of product focused on one benefit – its products Krack (for cracked heels) Moov (For lower back pain) and D'Cold (for colds) have a single-mended focus, an attribute, which Al Rlis and Jack Trout Spore of as being the most important component of effective position by strategy. While competitors sold general purpose creams Paras highlighted one impotent benefit, which stuck in consumers models. Hence this book is related to the present research work.

Nargundken Rajendra (2008) "International Marketing" Excel Books, New Delhi.

N Ayar Atul (2008) has written a book on fundamental of marketing. The book content 12 chapters about marketing, marketing research sales promotion, pricing process and so on. Chapter seven managing products the author highlighted on the no-name generic boarding. Certain supplies supply products that are intentionally "brandless". These products are mostly basic commodity-type products that consumer or business customers purchase as low price alternations to branded product. Hence this is helpful for the present research work.

Nayar Atul (2008) "Fundamentals of Marketing" Excel Books, , New Delhi.

Nargundkhar Rajendra (2008):

In his study, the author has given in the fifth chapter about the world class brands/marketers in Indian, which he has been highlighten on the Paras Pharma deserves to be recognized for its clever marketing of product focused on one benefit – its products Krack (for cracked heels) Moov (For lower back pain) and D'Cold (for colds) have a single-mended focus, an attribute, which Al Rlis and Jack Trout Spore of as being the most important component of effective position by strategy. While competitors sold general purpose creams Paras highlighted one impotent benefit, which stuck in consumers models. Hence this book is related to the present research work.

Nargundken Rajendra (2008) "International Marketing" Excel Books, New Delhi.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study has attempted to investigate the emerging trends in pharmaceutical industry of generic medicine in India. Looking at the nature of the topic and its scope, the methodology of study has to combine the library research and the online. The library research was aimed at survey of literature, compilation of secondary sources of information and cutting out the theoretical information that could help in building up to conceptual foundation of the subject.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Following are the objective of this study

- I] To study the current trends in Generic medicine.
- II] To study overall impact of Generic medicine.

CONCLUSION

A bird's eye view on the changing scenario of pharmaceutical industry of generic medicine in India is discussed in this Research paper . The generic drug was not too inferior to the branded drug. This shows that the generic drug can be used in the place of branded drug. With the concern of the physician, the practice of generic drug usage can be encouraged in the developing countries like India in some of the conditions where the drug has to be taken for longer period. But, changing a drug from a generic to branded or vice versa without the physician concern in the treatment should not be

encouraged which may affect the bioavailability and their therapeutic benefits. The government is also taking efforts to promote generic medicine the Prime Minister **NARENDRA MODI** guided doctors to prescribe generic medicine will help to poor people in India

REFERENCE

- Keegen J. Warren (2008) Global Marketing Management., Prentice Hall, inc. ISBN-97-8-81-203-2066-6.
- Nargundken Rajendra (2008) “International Marketing” Excel Books, New Delhi
- Nayar Atul (2008) “Fundamentals of Marketing” Excel Books, , New Delhi.
- Nargundken Rajendra (2008) “International Marketing” Excel Books, New Delhi.
- <http://www.myvmc.com/treatments/generic-medicines-and-branded-medicines/#C10>
- <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/law-soon-to-ensure-doctors-prescribe-cheaper-generic-drugs-assures-pm/articleshow/58231392.cms>
- <http://www.cormedicalgroup.com/heart-health-blog/generics>
- <http://www.bcbsm.com/index/health-insurance-help/faqs/plan-types/pharmacy/generic-drug-faq.html>
- <http://Wikipedia.com>